

The International Professional and Applied Management Review
incorporating

The International Journal of Professional Management
ISSN 20422341

The Journal of the International Professional Managers Association
And
IPE Management School, Paris

A Review of the Entrepreneurship Ecosystem of Oman

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Abstract

This conceptual work critically reviews existing initiatives of Oman for entrepreneurial growth. It focuses on the existing stakeholders of the entrepreneurship ecosystem of Oman, their work and potential for viable interventions for further entrepreneurship. The conceptual information here relates to Oman only. The study disseminates vital information on how entrepreneurs can benefit from the entrepreneurship ecosystem for developing and expanding their existing businesses. This ecosystem is in a developmental stage with recently incorporated organisations in growth. Challenges always remain as a pinnacle, and encouragement is given for opportunity entrepreneurship, rather than necessity entrepreneurship.

1. Introduction

Oman is fortunate in having oil and gas which has made it one of the wealthiest countries on the planet, but high reliance on these resources makes it vulnerable to economic instability of oil and gas prices (Oman Economic Review, 2016). Decreasing this reliance is essential for sustainable economic improvement (Schwab, 2016). This includes growing the non-hydrocarbon sector in the gross domestic product (GDP) which can be achieved expanding the economy (Supreme Council for Planning, 2016). The Omani government has considered enlarging the role of the private sector as an instrument in GDP. In this situation, the private sector has moved towards small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which involves particular strategies, arrangements and execution programmes This is helped by assessing the practices of industrial countries that have prospered in accelerating SMEs and entrepreneurship and have developed a complete ecosystem (Feld, 2012) capturing different determinants of entrepreneurship movements at microeconomic and macroeconomic levels (Obadic,2013). Several developing countries, including Oman, are working to update their entrepreneurship ecosystems to achieve performance at the best level of industrial countries.

A first step to inspiring entrepreneurship is mapping and gauging the existing entrepreneurial ecosystem in Oman. This allows for analysis of possible challenges and chances that can be tackled during particular interventions (Supreme Council for Planning, 2016). Entrepreneurial ecosystems are usually attractive in terms of their educational strength or their physical characteristics that give new opportunities(Acs, et al., 2014). At the initial point every entrepreneur needs some type of support to get started and gain stimulus and power

to help each day of business activity (Mason & Brown, 2013) The type of support needed depends on the type of business, and needs will change over time. Particularly in developing countries, people have enthusiasm for self-employment and entrepreneurship, but support is not always available (Marcotte,2014). The basics of entrepreneurship ecosystems have different roles in attracting and empowering people to become entrepreneurs, which is good for individuals and for the country.

A key aspect of entrepreneurial ecosystems is to emphasise the importance of entrepreneurship, both for individuals and for the country. (Stam, 2015). Its principle is to attract those who have the dream of being self-employed but do not fully understand the entrepreneurship concept, and those who are in need of help from the government. The entrepreneurial ecosystems concept has been argued by many authors regarding the impact on influencing the creation of new firms and new entrepreneurs (Isenberg, 2011). Oman has recognised the role of entrepreneurs as actors; able to add to economic development and be the agents of a new wealth making. However, entrepreneurship ecosystems in Oman are questionable as the concept itself is novel, and is not emphasised in most of the Oman economy

2. Literature review

The concept of entrepreneurial ecosystems relates to the individual and institutional attributes which either promote or discard the entrepreneur's inclination to take risks Professor Daniel Isenberg from Babson College stressed its importance in the Harvard Business Review (Isenberg 2010). The essential thoughts were first developed in the 1980s and 1990s, when research began to go beyond the individual and look at social, cultural, and economic influences (Stangler & Bell-Masterson 2015).

These general field areas contain numerous factors that assist in highly difficult and distinguishing circumstances. Recognising common causes is of limited value. Isenberg focuses on the significance of the concepts for each ecosystem under a unique set of conditions. This mostly overlaps with the well-known nine features and eight pillars as described by the World Economic Forum (2014). The primary consideration is that entrepreneurial ecosystems do not appear just anywhere. They require fruitful soil (Tsvetkova, 2015) and may appear where there is already a strong knowledge foundation and there are important figures in science and engineering (Mack & Mayer, 2016). Knowledge institutions such as research and development departments, in universities, companies, and the public sector, are good resources for skillful workers who begin businesses. However, the full benefit will not be gained without a receptive business environment and good use of technology. This is like an ecosystem which instead of looking at organisms looks at organisations (Arshed et al (2014). As said by Feldman (2014), "entrepreneurial ecosystems focus on cultures, institutions, and networks that have built up over time, rather than the appearance of order within global markets"

The success of an ecosystem centres on key features such as human capital, funding, and services. The players concerned are the talent, investors, mentors, advisors, entrepreneurial peers. There also needs to be an official government and regulatory framework, and unofficial institutions (cultural support) facilitating entrepreneurship and contact with consumers overseas (Casadesus- et al. 2013).

The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM, 2016) categorises entrepreneurs into two behavioural types, necessity entrepreneurs and opportunity entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship is a necessity in localities where there is no better alternative employment. Unemployment itself may open their eyes to possibilities. Opportunity entrepreneurs follow business opportunities or individual interests as their preferred way forward, whether or not employment is available. There is an urgent need to highlight how the existing elements of

entrepreneurial ecosystems can help entrepreneurs to grow their business in Oman. Articles on this subject are scarce, which indicates a delay in research in the academic field. The concept of entrepreneurial ecosystems needs deep research (Guo & Ahlstrom 2016).

3. Elements of the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Oman

There was wide participation from various stakeholders in the Oman entrepreneurship ecosystem. For the purposes of this study, we identified and streamlined nine main pillars and components.

3.1 Human capital workforce

Large amounts of human capital are a fundamental forerunner for achievement in the modern knowledge economy, and trained employees are a key component of the effectiveness of new challenges (Debrulle, et al, 2014).

This includes both specialised employees and qualified bosses who can help business visionaries as their organisations develop and excel. Together entrepreneurs and employees use their social networks to find excellent matches, including intense social networks inside a country (Al-Harrasi, 2014). Workers in supportive entrepreneurial ecosystems need additional technical skills; they need to accept risk as entrepreneurs themselves in order to succeed in the muddled environment of a business set up. The accessibility of skillful employees ready to rise to these challenges is a key area of new risks.

The Omani government has been dynamic in labour market intervention during its controversial job nationalisation programme (Omanisation). This seeks to incorporate local labour and decrease overseas labour in the public and private sector (Swales et al, 2012). This relates to the view that the local workforce lack the required skills, knowledge, and good work ethics (Schwab, 2016).

3.2 Accessible markets

The marketplace is a significant mode of governance in entrepreneurial ecosystems. It is mostly concerned with the scope and enforcement of government regulations and their role in attracting or restraining business activities. (Ahlstrom & Ding, 2014). Market access is accordingly a real test for new entrepreneurs with new ideas for potentially disruptive products. These entrepreneurs tend to be unaccustomed to government regulations, procurement methods, commercial accounting and business practices. Since 1971 the government of Oman has adopted an open market strategy to bring in local and overseas investment in almost all areas. Oman is not an active exporting country yet. Non-oil exports comprised only 13.5% of total exports in 2017 (NCSI, 2017). Several government efforts have sought to improve the industrialised sector's influence on the economy. On the other hand, there are several challenges, such as having a small limited marketplace, little marketplace purchasing power, competitive imported products, and weak links to export marketplaces which limit new business set ups (Porter, 2004).

3.3 Education and training

This basic factor is useful to help and enhance the knowledge of entrepreneurs in diverse fields. Mainly, it aids entrepreneurs to completely recognise the range of approaches to establishing, running and developing a versatile business (Nambisan & Baron, 2013). For instance, this factor paves the way for entrepreneurs to do something in their general area of their expertise, with additional training in new techniques, new technology, bookkeeping, laws, regulations and taxes. (Kassean et al, 2015). Many entrepreneurs have revealed that their basics were different, and not in the right area at present, and many had no idea

how to go about it smoothly. These people often only identify their weaknesses after incorporation Paço, et al, 2015).

The educational system in Oman, has been promoting memorising and imitating rather than encouraging novelty and (Belwal, et al, 2015) and there are no serious initiatives for encouraging innovative teaching. Currently, there is no business-linked awareness in the curriculum. The government is spending significant amounts on education, yet the outcomes have been unsatisfactory. Students have graduated without the talents they need to thrive in employment. Also, the proportion of illiterate youths and jobless people is very high in Oman.

The Ministry of Manpower has come up with a proposal called SANAD, which focuses on start-up entrepreneurship awareness campaigns. This is linked with the Omanisation programme which limits some sectors to Omani nationals. SANAD provides assistance in obtaining micro-loans from development banks in Oman, which requires initiative in joint ventures.

But this model in realism has not been effective and there are a lot of failures throughout the country. A recent survey revealed that 14% of companies are constantly promoting their staff with training and growth. It can be concluded that managers are not tracing the right talents from outside.

3.4 Funding and finance

Accessibility of finance is an additional vital element of entrepreneurial ecosystems. It includes the gathering of investors to promote funding. Attracting investors is of vital importance both when sowing the seeds of the business, and to develop and to sustain it (Wang, 2017). Investment could take the form of offering loans at a low interest rate. Seed capital financing is another area where Oman has a severe shortage (Pasmad, 2016). Existing public channel resources for venture capital and angel financing are not available at present. For instance, a joint stock corporation, Fund for Development of youth Projects, the first venture capital fund, incorporated 1998, focused on aborigines of 20-40 years of age, and those who could obtain a maximum of 49% of seed capital. But this fund was not processed for a couple of years. The main reasons have not been identified, but it was assumed that the main reasons were lack of experienced management to assess entrepreneurial requirements. In 2008 the fund went through a restructuring process, as a new board and director took over, yet small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) still have difficulties in accessing funding.

According to the latest executive view survey by the World Economic Forum (WEF), 13.5% of respondents considered financing as one of the most challenging features for business in Oman. One of the recent obstacles is that small borrowers often lack the detailed and historical financial proofs that banks rely on to evaluate creditworthiness. This is also reflected in the World Bank's credit information index, which places the Sultanate below UAE, Kuwait. Omani commercial banks have been reluctant to lend to small businesses. An exception is the Oman Development Bank, which offers SMEs loans at a rate of 9%.

3.5 Technology

Entrepreneurship, technology and innovation are jointly helpful. Technology offers entrepreneurs novel instruments to develop the effectiveness and output of their business, or new policies on which to make their ventures. In turn, entrepreneurs stimulate technological innovation by developing new or existing merchandise, services or practices and guaranteeing commercialisation (Arrotta, et al. 2014). Current conditions

in Oman, The wishes of the Omani people for diversification of the national economy, and the change towards a knowledge-based economy, has led to the view that research institutes and universities should focus generally on applied research. However, the lack of research and innovation policies has led the researcher to focus on interest-driven activities rather than policy-driven activities. The lack of research and innovation policies in addition to unfinished research and innovation infrastructure is seen to be holding back the entrepreneurial approach.

Generally, Oman's scientific and technology research base is in its developmental stage. Global Competitiveness Report, Oman's rankings were:

- Innovation – 66
- Scientific research – 103
- Private sector research and development – 86
- Industry-research cooperation – 86

There is no significant improvement in any of these activities at state level. There is very lethargic improvement at the state level. The culture of research and development is new in almost all sectors at individual, industry, and government level. Some exceptions are the Ministry of Commerce and Ministry of Agriculture and the Sultan Qaboos University who published 88 research articles in 2008 (SQU, 2008). There was only one US registered patent from an Omani company and that was in 1993 (Porter, 2004). There was neither technology nor innovation in industry or academia. A small 2.8% of the population has internet connectivity. However, the government has directed the Information Technology Authority (ITA) to take the initiative to convert to a knowledge-based society, by overseeing e-Oman programmes.

3.6 Culture

Culture has been identified as a key element in maintaining entrepreneurial ecosystems, including social customs and approaches (Isenberg, 2011). Developing culture is like building people, especially young people who are focused on starting businesses rather than seeking employment from others (Azar, & Drogendijk, 2016). Some good Omani entrepreneurs have come up bravely with an initiative to generate jobs, and these people are much appreciated, but not universally. It has been noted that culture is an extremely dependent factor. A person with a government job or military rank is often regarded with confidence, whereas a successful entrepreneur is not. In Omani society successful self-sufficient role models are scarce. Culture and social customs in Oman are similar to those in other Arab countries. These factors have discouraged the entry of novel business in Oman.

3.7 Administration

Here we are considering government policies and practices that favour entrepreneurs. Frequent policy changes bring insecurity and discourage entrepreneurship, but policies can also be helpful, e.g., through the improvement of infrastructure services favourable to business (Guo et al, 2016). It is a myth that the government has created rules to support entrepreneurs through start-up funds. Moreover the licensing formalities at the stage of incorporation has bureaucracy, restrictions and complexities, which are considered the most demotivating feature for business (World Competitive Report, 2017). Oman was ranked 65 out of 183 with respect to the smooth-running of business in 2016 (World Bank, 2016), just above Namibia and Rwanda. Currently there are three government Ministries involved in small business development – Ministry of Manpower, Ministry of Commerce,

and Ministry of Social Development. A structured policy framework for small entrepreneurs is still lacking in government regulations.

3.8 Infrastructure

This refers to the facilities needed for entrepreneurs to expand the existing business, such as hiring marketing and improvement facilities including other physical infrastructures (Fain & Wagner, 2014). Authentic infrastructure is a decisive factor for upcoming entrepreneurs in meeting customer demand (Bouncken et al, 2016). Poor administration and corruption make bad entrepreneurship worse and blocks growth.

According to the 2014 World Economic Forum Report, Oman's rankings, out of 139 countries, were:

- Excellence of overall infrastructure – 21
- Quality of roads – 10
- Quality of port infrastructure – 33

A few of the factors affecting this are stable traffic developments, lack of infrastructure in certain remote areas, and frequent floods. At present the government is investing more in expanding the road networks, airport and seaport. The first and only IT park, Knowledge Oasis Muscat (KOM), situated in Muscat, was initiated by the Ministry of Commerce and Industry. It is hosting around 60 regional and international businesses including Microsoft and many others. KOM is running the only business programme, The Knowledge Mine (TKMP) which provides subsidised office space and other technology-related services for entrepreneurs. The drawback of this programme is that it can only accommodate only 15 new firms.

3.9 Universities and institutions

The entrepreneurial university theme has attracted attention as part of a broader context of rising knowledge-based economies (Rasmussen, et al. 2014). It is linked with increasing pressures facing universities to add to socio-economic growth (Curi, et al, 2012). This pressurises universities to make modifications at various levels, from organisational measurements, academic and knowledge production measurement, formation of organisational connections between universities and outside entities (industry and government), and the cultural and beliefs dimension (Siegel, & Wright. 2015). This has also led to governments around the world, particularly in Oman, launching public policies to sustain and promote universities as entrepreneurial bodies. These policies appear to focus on knowledge commercialisation by encouraging universities to collaborate with industry. The most significant role for universities is to set up a community of students who convey new thoughts and surge the intellectual capability of the community. The Omani government considers the knowledge-based economy to be a good choice for sustainable socio-economic growth, and sees Omani universities as playing a crucial role in this aspiration.

In most Omani university departments there is no movement linked to campus-wide entrepreneurship awareness, entrepreneurship education programmes, or inter-disciplinary problem-based learning. However, recently there have been some modest initiatives introducing optional entrepreneurial courses at SQU. Student education is affected by the country being an oil-based economy, that offers free education for all and a safe job after graduation. This cultural attitude affects the education system as a whole, and university education programmes in particular.

Despite the obvious desire from national authorities to shift towards a knowledge-based economy where education plays a crucial role, the learning environment is seen to be memorising-driven rather than knowledge-driven. Furthermore, extracurricular activities focus on sport, art, and traditional culture rather than entrepreneurial activities. In this context students aim to get good degrees in order to obtain prestigious governmental jobs. In general, Omani students are hesitant to practice self-employment as a career choice. This approach puts huge pressure on national authorities to offer secure jobs for increasing numbers of graduates every year.

This exploration stage gives us an essential observation of the current situation in Omani universities with respect to entrepreneurial activities.

4. Conclusion

The problem is not lack of entrepreneurship, but somewhat a negative macro environment and infrastructure, which pushes entrepreneurial activity into idle and damaging economic ways instead of wealth formation (Oman Economic Review 2016). In Oman most entrepreneurial activity does not focus on opportunity. People are forced to start up new businesses in order to survive due to high unemployment. Moreover most of these entrepreneurs are in the informal sectors of heavy expenses in the establishment stage, which also restricts their resources in expansion plans.

A stable entrepreneurial ecosystem in Oman is possible through a much improved and diversified economy, although some weaknesses can be identified in employment opportunities, Omani nationals need frequent notification and training on how to make use of existing entrepreneurial opportunities in mining, tourism and agriculture. This could be made practical by a much harmonised system of administration, especially in research and developmental institutions. Also, the government needs to launch some innovative programmes to promote research and development, creativity and sustainability.

The programme mapping has to be done jointly to achieve these entrepreneurial goals and other research and development practices. Recently the government of Oman has taken new steps and measures on entrepreneurship and innovations by realising that the state should not focus only on oil and gas exports, but should increase the number of SMEs, and work towards a knowledge-driven economy. In this context the Research Council has come up with the idea of converting student projects into start-ups by proper funding. This will promote innovation in the country's economic development.

The Sultanate is mainly depending on government institutions in almost all sectors. A stable and fine policy programme that can unite entrepreneurial activities will have an impact on the country's economic success. For this Oman needs a much wider entrepreneurship policy approach, including coordination of several bodies including both the private and the public sector. The government needs to give guidance by playing a major role in administering the policy programmes. The thrust needs to be on the quality and not the quantity of entrepreneurship sustained programmes. A highly resilient and committed government unit has to be formed with all the ministerial powers to govern and advocate entrepreneurship and its further development. Finally, the focus has to be on opportunity entrepreneurship rather than necessity entrepreneurship so as to safeguard the future of Oman.

5. Recommendations

Various objectives need to be the focus in order to promote a healthy climate for entrepreneurship in Oman:

1. Analysis of the ecosystem, focusing not only on result-oriented entrepreneurship but also on the restricted factors such as educational and societal qualities. This will enable reconstruction of an overall ecosystem.
2. Woman youth entrepreneurs need to be increased through diversity to bring entrepreneurial promotion. The study of ecosystems should centre not only on results but also on the restricted educational, societal and material qualities that sustain entrepreneurial action, and the ways in which these qualities work in tandem and recreate the overall ecosystem.
3. Policymakers should connect in open dialogue with entrepreneurs to discover ecosystem solutions that are suitable for home conditions in Oman.
4. Creating networks among large companies and emerging entrepreneurs should be ingredients in any public policy to improve entrepreneurship. Confidence and contacts are vital for achieving success in business in Oman.
5. Educators and society leaders must promote traditions that sustain entrepreneurial ambitions and bring success stories to Oman.
6. Entrepreneurs themselves must be in a position to direct the promotion of ecosystems in Oman, by generating entrepreneurial society and offering to contribute to strategy.
7. The different players in an entrepreneurship ecosystem in Oman should assist other stakeholders in building most of their particular strengths.
8. Entrepreneurs work best in a strategy and regulatory environment in Oman that holds few obstacles, provides incentives to innovation, and defends personal property.

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